

DIGITAL STORYTELLING TOOLS TO TEACH BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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Abstract

Technological developments in the 21st century, it's now necessary to integrate technological emendations effectively into the tutoring- learning surroundings. There were several approaches that allow integration of technology into tutoring- literacy process. One of these approaches is digital storytelling. The present abstract exploration concentrated on the Digital storytelling tools to educate Biological tools. Digital storytelling serves as a popular pedagogical tool to be used by preceptors in different fields for scholars from all age groups, from education situations. The process of producing a digital story requires scholars first to determine a subject, to probe the subject, and to form a script within the frame of their exploration. Following this, the process requires scholars to associate their scripts with similar multimedia rudiments as images, music and plates and to form short stories by using several software's. scholars completing the process of digital storytelling process can partake their stories with a certain followership in class or on the Internet. participating digital stories could help scholars understand each other and show empathy towards one another. In addition, it also allows scholars to get information about a number of subjects. The present paper focused on the Digital storytelling tools to teach Biological Science with prime objectives are (i) To understand the concept of Digital storytelling tools. (ii) To discuss the Digital storytelling tools to teach Biological Sciences. (iii) To analyze the importance of Digital storytelling tools to teach Biological Sciences. The methodology of the exploration is a different type involving an interpretive, discussion, observation and study secondary sources, like books, papers, journals, thesis, university news, expert opinion, and websites, etc.

Key Words: Digital storytelling tools, Biological Science

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Introduction:

Preceptors in the 21st century believe that technology can be an effective tool in educating the new generation, making literacy pretensions easier to achieve. Technology has long been used in classrooms to condense educational styles used by preceptors. Technology plays a central part in digital storytelling, an educational system that’s seeing more common use in classrooms moment. According to Smeda e tal (2014), digital storytelling is an innovative pedagogical approach that can “ engage scholars in deep and meaningful literacy. ”

Digital storytelling is an effective multimedia tool that supports tutoring and literacy while perfecting pupil provocation. ” Digital storytelling refers to the practice of using computer- grounded tools to tell stories or present ideas. Digital stories have also been defined as multimedia donations that combine a variety of digital rudiments within a narrative structure for Biological tools.

Alismail (2015) further states that multimedia tools similar as digital storytelling provides scholars with openings to share and interact in the classroom, while gaining new chops similar as conflation, analysis, and evaluation. Dillon (2014) also lists down a number of benefits associated with using digital storytelling as an educational tool for Biological Science.

Digital storytelling as an educational tool for Biological Science:

Fig. 1- Digital storytelling as an educational tool for Biological Science

Digital storytelling creates space for meaningful listening:

Digital stories give scholars with the occasion to digest information in a meaningful way. This is particularly important in an age where people are bombarded with stories and information. Digital stories allow preceptors to authentically engage scholars in the story’s communication.

Digital storytelling persuades the brain and the heart:

Digital stories can educate scholars the value of emotional rhetoric, allowing them to explore new ways of acting or allowing else. These stories can evoke emotional responses in scholars and encourage them to pursue motifs that they 're passionate about.

The method allows students to showcase their learning to their peers:

Students benefit not only from receiving information through digital stories but also from making digital stories that feature their experiences and learnings. The many aspects of creating a digital story improve students' technical skills and hone research and writing skills as well.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the concept of Digital storytelling tools.
2. To discuss the Digital storytelling tools to teach Biological Sciences.
3. To analyze the importance of Digital storytelling tools to teach Biological Sciences.

Uses of Digital storytelling tools to educate Biological tools:

- ✓ In the area of education, storytelling conditioning support the development of language, which is suggestive, social and open, and increases the vocabulary of children.
- ✓ These conditioning give children the occasion to break problems, use their imagination, develop their creativity, and reflect their inner Earth.
- ✓ Digital storytelling is a technological operation that can be served from to make it possible for scholars to learn the subjects in a better way and for preceptors to use technology in their classes in a more effective manner.
- ✓ The process of creating, designing, writing, and presenting the design of a digital story is effective in terms of the development of scholars' chops related to doing exploration, jotting, organizing, using technology, donation, canvassing, communication and cooperation, problem- working and evaluation.

Digital storytelling tools to educate Biological Science

VoiceThread, Adobe Creative Cloud Express, Twine, and ArcGIS Story charts are tools that can support the creation of digital stories for Biological Science. A platform where druggies can produce, partake and annotate media systems which incorporate videotape, images, audio, and text-book.

Fig. 2- Digital storytelling tools to teach Biological Science

1. VoiceThread:

As a classroom schoolteacher, sound assessment practices have always been a challenge, especially as we strive towards meeting the different requirements of all of our learners. This challenge becomes indeed more complex due to isolation, descriptive feedback, and the different technological tools our scholars are using to communicate their literacy. Throw in a gusto of Problem or Inquiry- grounded Learning and you have the perfect storm of open literacy openings, leaving you to wonder how you're going to capture anything.

VoiceThread is a tool that comes alive once added to. The simplicity of dragging and dropping a wide variety of lines, or snapping a picture or videotape through the app that can be annotated and or reflected on, simplifies the assessment process allowing for constant, immediate feedback. Descriptive feedback is made easy through the voice recording, and enhanced by the capability to annotate directly on whatever you have uploaded.

2. Adobe Creative Cloud Express

Adobe Express generators will soon enjoy expanded videotape editing powers with a new mixed-media editor, Generative AI capabilities to help induce unique sources, images and new backgrounds, and new openings to unite with other generators across other Adobe Creative Cloud apps, delivering lesser productivity. Lately added inventions in Adobe Express include:

- **Quick Actions**, making it easy for users to quickly remove background features from photos, refine cutouts, trim and merge videos, turn videos into GIFs, create QR codes and convert/export PDFs in a few clicks.
- **AI-Driven Template Recommendations**, delivering customized collections of relevant templates based on the project already being worked on.
- **Content Scheduler**, giving users the ability to collaborate, plan, schedule, preview and publish social media content across platforms – all from one place.
- **Multi-Page Capabilities**, providing the ability to create multiple social media assets, logos, banners, flyers and more, easily adding consistent branding to each page.

3. ArcGIS Story Maps:

ArcGIS Story Maps is a story authoring web-based application that allows you to share your maps in the context of narrative text and other multimedia content. You can use ArcGIS Story Maps to do the following:

- ✓ Author stories with the story builder. Stories can include charts, narrative textbook, lists, images, vids, bedded particulars, and other media.
- ✓ Publish and partake your stories. Published stories each have their own URL, and you can use these URLs to partake your stories within your association, to specific groups, or with everyone.
- ✓ Produce and publish collections. Collections can include stories and ArcGIS web apps whisked together for easy sharing and presenting.
- ✓ Manage your stories. View and edit your stories from the Stories runner, find stories penned by others in your association, and add stories to your favourites list.

Digital storytelling tool in Biological Science:

- ✓ It captures the individual stories of scholars in your classroom, celebrates their oneness, develops their individual voice and helps them learn that their story has value.
- ✓ It gives scholars a choice about how to stylish tell the story they've inside them.
- ✓ Digital storytelling requires us to hear to others, erecting empathy and understanding for a point of view.
- ✓ Digital storytelling means that the true lived experience of each existent can be participated with the class, making for a further indifferent terrain.
- ✓ It allows scholars to come preceptors on a regular base.
- ✓ It gives a broader understanding of communication chops beyond the written word, allowing scholars to communicate in the spoken word, filmland, music and art.
- ✓ Digital storytelling is near to the kind of communication that's a part of ultramodern social media and allows us to help kiddies to understand it, while tutoring them prosocial morals and morals and prosocial actions for using them.
- ✓ Digital storytelling has shown to ameliorate the social and emotional intelligence of scholars.
- ✓ Digital Storytelling teaches important 21st century chops similar as digital knowledge, global knowledge, technological knowledge and Information knowledge.
- ✓ Digital storytelling is delightful. The kiddies are agitated to partake their stories, their classmates are agitated to watch them and preceptors are agitated to grade them.

Digital Storytelling and Bioscience Teacher:

Digital Storytelling tool is the innovative conception in Bioscience tutoring. preceptors plays a important part in the success of Digital Storytelling at the academy.

If the preceptors aren't completely comfortable and confident with the Digital storytelling tool to tutoring, also there will be a limited impact on the tutoring- literacy process.

preceptors has to be developed their mind set to integrate the rearmost technology in the

Bioscience classroom tutoring:

- ✓ Preceptors should also know the right station and values, besides being complete in chops related to tutoring.
- ✓ School teacher is responsible for creating the warm terrain in the class. He prepares the literacy openings that helps the scholars in using the assignments of Digital Storytelling tool. Accordingly, it's pivotal that all the preceptors should be prepared to give their scholars with these openings.
- ✓ Preceptors training program helps the preceptors to acquire the introductory chops and capabilities to come a good schoolteacher.
- ✓ Technology acts as the gateway to acquire further information which helps the schoolteacher to come update.

Advantages of Digital Storytelling in Biological Science:

- ❖ Advantages of digital storytelling were examined, it was seen that digital storytelling contributed to the ephemerality of what they learned, increased their literacy and allowed making use of multimedia rudiments as well as use of imagination.
- ❖ In addition, the preservice preceptors reported that they were more active in these surroundings; that the digital storytelling conditioning were amusing; that these conditioning could draw their attention and develop their exploration chops; and that the conditioning increased the pupil- schoolteacher relationship, helped take responsibility and acquire the technology chops, supported literacy by doing and living, contributed to learning new effects and allowed saving time.
- ❖ The preservice preceptors substantially stated that use of multimedia rudiments in the digital storytelling process would contribute to the ephemerality of the subjects learned and that this would increase scholars' literacy. In addition, they reported that the process could grease tutoring.
- ❖ Some of the preservice preceptors reported that creating a digital story could develop scholars' technology use chops. One of the preservice preceptors, stated that the scholars used technology intensely and effectively, saying "Digital storytelling requires use of technology and helps learn how to use technology in similar situations.

- ❖ It also helps both the schoolteacher and the scholars learn how to use technology effectively and productively. ”

Limitations of Digital Storytelling:

- ❖ Biological Science preservice preceptors’ views about the negative aspects of digital storytelling were examined, it was seen that subjects are tutored superficially in the digital storytelling process; that it wasn't possible to borrow digital storytelling to all subjects; and that different readiness situations of the scholars would have negative influence on the process.
- ❖ The preservice preceptors substantially reported that digital storytelling didn't allow presenting detailed information about subjects and those scholars were handed with superficial information about subjects.

Outcomes:

Digital Storytelling tool playing very significant role in Teaching-Learning for Bioscience Subject. Following are the outcomes of using the Digital Storytelling tool in Teaching-Learning of Bioscience.

- ❖ Bioscience background teachers have a more favorable attitude than Arts/Social Science background teachers towards using the Digital Storytelling tool.
- ❖ Assist seniors in accessing Digital Storytelling tool and effectively.
- ❖ Motivate undergraduate-centered and self-directed learning.
- ❖ For educational enhancement through Digital Storytelling tool, Produce a creative learning environment of Bioscience.
- ❖ Digital Storytelling tool promote collaborative learning in a distance learning situation for Bioscience.
- ❖ Digital Storytelling tool offer more opportunities to advance critical (higher-order) thinking skills for Bioscience.
- ❖ Digital Storytelling tool for Bioscience, better education, including collecting quality.
- ❖ Using Digital Storytelling tool, support teaching by facilitating entrance to course content.

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